

FATIGUE DAMAGE ASSESSMENT OF C45 SAMPLES VIA DIFFERENT EXPERIMENTAL MEASUREMENTS AND MICROSTRUCTURAL INVESTIGATIONS

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In this work, the fatigue damage evolution has been monitored by using the Electrical Resistance Change (ERC) method on a batch of unnotched C45 carbon steel samples. The experimental test plan involved several fatigue tests at different stress ratios selected between $R = 0.1$ and $R = 0.5$ with the aim of evaluating the influence of the mean load. Static tensile tests have been carried out before fatigue tests. Also, during these tests, the electrical resistance changes were measured. The results obtained from the static tests highlighted that the electrical resistance underwent an initial reduction in the elastic field of 4% and then grew regularly with an increase of 40% in the plastic phase. The variations in electrical resistance measured as the fatigue life varied were instead characterised by a rapid initial increase of about 6%, followed by a constant trend until final failure. This trend was justified on the basis of the evident progressive deformation of the transversal section of the material.

Keywords: Fatigue of metals, Damage evolution, Structural monitoring, Electrical resistance

INTRODUCTION

Fatigue damage of materials has been the subject of numerous experimental research (Palit Sagar et al. [1], Xia et al. [2], Mei et al. [3], Prasse et al. [4], Wang et al. [5]) aimed at identifying experimental parameters for studying the evolution of the damage phenomena and possibly predict the final failure in advance, pursuing a structural integrity monitoring. In general, fatigue loading leads to an irreversible degradation of the elastic and conductive properties of the material due to the onset of microstructural changes linked to the accumulation of fatigue damage. Klesnil et al. [6], studied that fatigue damage is mainly due to the formation of slip bands, extrusion or intrusion of the latter, nucleation of microcracks, growth and coalescence, initiation and propagation of macroscopic cracks which lead to the definitive failure of the material. These phenomena can be simultaneously or partially present (Sevostianov et al. [7]).

In the literature there are various techniques proposed for fatigue monitoring: several examples are the recent developments of thermographic techniques (Middleton et al. [8], Rajic et al. [9], Vassilopoulos et al. [10], Palumbo et al. [11], and De Finis et al. [12]), based on the study of thermal dissipative phenomena that arise within a cyclically stressed material, as well as the study of the variation in the propagation speed of ultrasound in a material subjected to fatigue (Omari et al. [13] and Dattoma et al. [14]).

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The method here proposed has received limited attention in terms of structural monitoring on metals and is based on the measurement of the Electrical Resistance Change (ERC). This technique has been applied instead in numerous studies to detect damage on CFRP composites as a parameter sensitive to the crack nucleation and propagation phase and in general to the fatigue damage process (Park et al. [15], Nobile et al. [16], Fischer et al. [17], Schulte et al. [18], Motahhari et al. [19]).

Historically, the first studies on ERC technique date back to the years 1960-1990 (Tanaka et al. [20], Lemaitre et al. [21], Robins and Charsley [22], Basinski et al. [23], Starke et al. [24], Lawson and Meshii [25]) and concerned the study of the relationship between damage and resistivity. The research subsequently focused on the definition of a damage parameter based on the measurement of electrical resistance.

In a previous work published by the authors [16], the Electrical Resistance Change (ERC) was measured during fatigue tests of carbon steel C45 notched specimens at different stress amplitude levels at a fixed stress ratio. The comparison of the resistance data measured in the initial phases and in the following phases of fatigue highlighted the existence of measurable variations linked to the progression of fatigue damage.

Starting from the experimental results already obtained by Nobile et al. [16], the aims of the present research are:

- Confirm the feasibility of using electrical resistance variations as an indicator of fatigue damage through a larger and more systematic experimental campaign,
- Study the resistance variation in a uniform tension field, using constant section specimens,
- Evaluate the effect of the stress ratio on the electrical resistance variations.

The experimental results showed variations in electrical resistance, profoundly influenced by the plasticisation phenomena of the material. Despite the potential of the technique, it was found that the correct interpretation of the experimental data for the purposes of predicting the residual fatigue life still requires further effort for a correct evaluation of the physical phenomena at the origin of the measured variations.

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The specimens used for static and fatigue tests using the ERC technique are made of C45 carbon steel, which geometry and nominal dimensions are shown in Figure 1a-b.

FIGURE 1 Geometry of the C45 specimens used for the static (a) and fatigue (b) tests

First of all, the mechanical properties of the material were determined through static tests, which has been repeated on three specimens. During the static tests, the change in electrical resistance of the gauge length was measured, using the same test setup used for the fatigue tests. The tensile curves (Fig. 2a-b) and the mechanical properties of the steel (Table 1) are consistent with the data presented in the literature.

FIGURE 2 Mechanical properties of C45 steel: Stress-strain curves (a); determination of the elastic modulus (b)

TABLE 1 Values of global evaluation parameters obtained for selected specimens

Specimen	Yield stress σ_y [MPa] (0.2%)	Young's modulus E [GPa]	Tensile strength (UTS) σ_u [MPa]	Poisson's modulus ν
T1	563	184.7	759	0.3
T2	486	192.7	774	
T3	455	195.6	750	
Average values	501	191.0	761	
Standard deviation	56	6	12	

Resistance measurements were made using a typical 4-wire setup, injecting electrical current through two external electrodes, and measuring resistance from the voltage drop, through two internal electrodes. During test, the temperature varied as a result both of the applied load and of the Joule effect due to the injected electric current. Therefore, the surface temperature of the specimen was measured simultaneously through two T-type thermocouples applied in the middle of the gauge length. Using this data, it would be possible to correct the raw resistance data, to account for the variation in electrical resistance induced by the temperature variations.

The experimental setup adopted (Fig. 3) allows measurements to be carried out during the execution of mechanical tests, without the need to interrupt the tests and remove the specimen from the testing machine. It includes a direct current generator (model KEITHLEY 2260B-B0-27 720W), an Agilent 34970 temperature data acquisition unit, which has a resolution of 6 ½ digits (22 bits) and

a basic accuracy of 0.004%, and a HBM Quantum X data acquisition for the measurements of the electrical voltage at the ends of the internal electrodes.

FIGURE 3 Experimental setup of fatigue monitoring using electrical resistance measurements

The electrical resistance between the two internal electrodes was determined using Ohm's law, based on the potential drop measured when a direct current of 3A is injected between the external electrical ends. For the purposes of correct execution of the measurements, the specimen and the extensometer were electrically insulated by placing sheets of insulating material on the gripped surfaces.

The electrodes for voltage measurement and the ones used for current injection were carefully positioned, symmetrical with respect to the centre line of the gauge length (Fig. 4a). The use of a mechanical spacer allowed the repetitive placement of electrodes with an estimated tolerance of ± 0.1 mm and the minimisation of the associated source of measurement errors (Fig. 4a). The possibility of using the same knives of an extensometer as electrical terminals for measuring electrical resistance was also evaluated. The measurement errors introduced by the setup could be discussed considering the equivalent measurement electrical circuit (Fig. 4b) that schematises the parasitic resistances due to the contact R_c and the sample resistance R_s . Assuming that R_c is the same for all cables, the 4-wire setup allows neglecting the influence of the cables, while the absolute value of R_s depends by electrode distance.

FIGURE 4 4-wire configuration: placement of measurement electrodes and thermocouples (a); electrical circuit diagram for ERC measurements (b)

Fatigue tests were performed using an MTS 810 servo-hydraulic loading machine equipped with a load cell of ± 100 kN. The specimens were subjected to tension-tension fatigue with different stress ratios ($R = 0.1$, $R = 0.3$, and $R = 0.5$) under load control with a sinusoidal waveform, load frequency of 9 Hz, imposing a constant maximum stress σ_{max} . The hysteresis cycles of the useful section of the material were determined using a 25 mm gauge length extensometer. Table 2 summarises the fatigue parameters of each specimen tested.

TABLE 2 Experimental parameters for each fatigue test (*Run Out).

Sample	Load frequency [Hz]	Stress ratio (R)	σ_{max} [MPa]	σ_m [MPa]	σ_a [MPa]	F_{max} [kN]	F_m [kN]	F_a [kN]	Number of cycles to failure (N_f)
P4	9	0.3	456.60	296.79	159.81	9.15	5.95	3.20	381178
P5	9	0.3	456.60	296.79	159.81	9.43	2.83	3.30	247655
P6	9	0.1	456.60	251.13	205.47	9.28	5.11	4.18	102639
P7	9	0.5	456.60	342.45	114.15	9.30	6.97	2.32	3164947*

During mechanical testing, the experimentally recorded ERC (ΔR_{exp}) is the sum of the variation induced by the temperature change and the variation induced by the irreversible fatigue damage process in the material.

$$\Delta R_{exp} = R_{exp} - R_0 = \Delta R_{th} + \Delta R_{damage} \quad (1)$$

The raw electrical resistance data were then corrected by subtracting the effect of the resistance variation due to temperature through the following relationship:

$$\Delta R_{th} = R - R_0 = A\Delta T \quad (2)$$

where A is the temperature coefficient of resistance expressed in $m\Omega \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ which depends on the material, the initial temperature, the geometry, and the temperature difference from the starting point ΔT . The constant A was determined experimentally for each type of specimen by correlating the variation in electrical resistance with the temperature measured by the thermocouples by heating the specimens with a halogen lamp.

The resistance coefficients due to temperature were evaluated by interpolating the experimental data obtained during the calibration tests. The experimental setup adopted for determining the resistance coefficients for temperature correction is shown in Figure 5a. The specimen was heated using a 1 kW halogen lamp, measuring the temperature data through two thermocouples (Type T), and measuring the corresponding change in electrical resistance using the same setup used for the mechanical tests. Figure 5b shows the increase in specimen temperature over time recorded by the thermocouples. The resistance coefficients determined on the specimen for the static and fatigue specimens, both with the electrical contacts and with the extensometer knives are shown in the following Table 3.

The trends of the variation in resistance measured with the electrical contacts and with the extensometer knives (Fig. 6), compared to the variation in the average temperature measured by the thermocouples, show a linear correlation between the two variables during the heating phase and the latter was used to determine the value of the A coefficients.

FIGURE 5 Experimental setup for the determination of the coefficient A (a); Trend of the thermal profile over time during the heating and cooling phase of the sample (b)

TABLE 3 Experimental determination of the thermal resistance coefficient A

Test	Detection method	A [$m\Omega/^{\circ}C$]
Static	Electrical contacts	0.0015
	Extensometer knives	0.0014
Fatigue	Electrical contacts	0.0007
	Extensometer knives	0.0007

FIGURE 6 Experimental resistance variation measured with the electrical contacts (a) and with the extensometer knives (b) against temperature variation for the determination of the coefficient A

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For all the mechanical tests, the results were reported in terms of the variation of electrical resistance normalised to the initial value of the resistance, in order to minimise the effect of the different

positioning of the electrodes on the sample surface. In Figure 7a-b, the variation in electrical resistance corrected as the deformation varies is shown for the specimens subjected to static test measured both with the electrical contacts and with the extensometer knives. The resistance first decreases of 4% in the initial phase of the test, when the sample is still in the elastic range, subsequently a rapid increase in the resistance is observed, which increases by 40% almost linearly with the deformation up to the necking, where it rapidly decreases (Fig. 7a). The latter behaviour is justified by the fact that the elongation of the sample grows more rapidly than the reduction of the cross section. Instead, the resistance measured by the extensometer knives increases with the deformation for the entire duration of the test, until the sample breaks, not being affected at all by the necking phenomenon. This behaviour could depend on the small contact area of the extensometer positioned in the centre of the specimen, which makes it not sensitive.

FIGURE 7 Trend of the variation of the corrected electrical resistance as the deformation measured in the static tests with the electrical contacts (a) and with the extensometer knives (b)

Concerning the results obtained for the fatigue tests, the average temperature measured by the thermocouples applied to the specimen underwent a rapid initial increase, followed by a more regular and contained increase for most of the fatigue life, until presenting an increase much faster in the final part immediately before the break (Figure 8a). The effect of the correction of the electrical resistance due to the temperature is limited for the tested specimens, as can be observed in the example shown in Figure 8b for the P5 specimen.

FIGURE 8 Temperature variation over time during fatigue tests for all tested samples (a); Effect of temperature correction for specimen P5 (b)

The electrical resistance data were averaged over a time interval of 10s for specimens P4, P5 and P6 and 20s for P7, obtaining the curves in Figure 9. The experimental measurements obtained using the extensometer contacts as electrical terminals (Fig. 9b) appear to be affected by higher experimental errors, probably due to the variation in electrical contact resistance of the knives on the surface of the material. For this reason, the curves that will be considered representative of the phenomenon are those shown in Figure 9a, which are all characterised by an initial increase in electrical resistance, which remains almost constant for the entire duration, not showing significant variations due to the advancement of fatigue damage. Furthermore, the curves obtained are not substantially influenced by the stress ratio used.

FIGURE 9 Change in normalised electrical resistance due to damage only as a function of fatigue life [%] measured by electrical contacts (a) and by the extensometer knives (b)

This trend differs from the curves obtained by the authors in a previous work (Nobile et al. [16]), obtained using the same experimental setup on notched specimens also made of C45 steel, where a decrease in electrical resistance was observed in the initial stages of fatigue life, followed by a sudden increase starting from 30-40% of fatigue life.

To justify the different trend obtained, the mechanical hysteresis loops obtained by measuring strain by the extensometer, were examined (Fig. 10a). The curves of Fig. 10 highlighted, for each test condition, a ratcheting behaviour that is characteristic of a significant progressive permanent deformation of the material.

FIGURE 10 Effect of progressive plastic deformation for specimens P6 (a), P5 (b) and P7 (c)

The gradual accumulation of plastic deformation therefore affects the entire resistant section of the specimen, a condition which determines a constancy of the measured electrical resistance, as has been demonstrated by Nobile et al. [16] through the execution of a Low-Cyclic Fatigue (LCF) test at amplitudes growing.

The accumulation of plastic deformation can be highlighted also by hardness measurements. As known, the plastic deformation of metallic materials is governed mainly by the slip mechanism of the dislocations. As plastic deformation proceeds, the dislocations interfere each other leading to multiplication/ intersections/ pile up/ tangles of defectiveness. All those phenomena inhibit the free slipping of dislocations and impose higher stress for having further deformation. Consequently, if the yield stress after plastic deformations is measured, it is found to increase proportionally to the degree of the plastic deformation. Finally, being the yield stress proportional to hardness, the hardness measurements can be also representative of the amount of plastic deformation.

As shown in Fig. 11a, micro-hardness Vickers measurement (HV 05/15s) were applied to the fractured sample both along the longitudinal fracture surface and perpendicular to it.

Along the X axis, both the indentation lines supplied similar trend in hardness measurements with a progressive increase as the distance from the reference edge (0 point in Fig.11a) increases. This result could highlight a non-uniform plastic deformation that accumulate mainly far from the reference edge, so, close to the edge, the fracture occurs without significant plastic deformation. The last result is confirmed by the value of the hardness of the undeformed C45 material that is equal to HV 212±2, very similar to the hardness found close to the reference edge (Fig. 11b).

FIGURE 11 Scheme of microhardness measurements and related longitudinal head of fractured sample after measurements (a) HV values as function of distance along X and Y axis (b) according to the scheme in (a)

The third indentation line was detected starting from the point of highest hardness along the fracture head and moving at increasing distance from the fracture head. It is interesting to observe that the hardness values along y axis progressively decreases as the distance from the fracture surface increases or, that is the same, as the plastic deformation decreases. So, the hardness of C45 undeformed material has reached at almost 6mm from the hardest point at the fracture head.

By analysing the mechanical hysteresis loops it was also possible to evaluate the stiffness degradation of the specimen and the total dissipated energy throughout material lifespan, also referred as area under hysteresis loop (Fig. 12a-b).

As it is possible to observe from Fig. 12a-b, both parameters present a steady state phase after the load imposition. In particular, the curves of Fig. 12a-b present a little scatter each one. Of course, more investigations are required to establish the statistical significance of these variations.

The behaviour of the normalised electrical resistance parameter (Fig. 9) is consistent with the curves of stiffness degradation and area under the hysteresis loop (Fig. 12a-b).

FIGURE 12 Curves representing the normalised stiffness (a) and of the area under the hysteresis loop (b) versus the number of cycles normalised by the total cycles (N/N_f). (The total number of cycles varies for all the tested specimens)

The analysis of the fracture surfaces (Fig. 13) finally confirmed the extremely ductile behaviour of the material, which was affected by significant macroscopic plastic deformations at the moment of final fatigue failure.

FIGURE 13 Analysis of the fracture surface observed with the stereomicroscope for sample P4 (side A and side B)

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the ERC electrical resistance method was applied on a batch of C45 carbon steel samples to monitor the onset and evolution of fatigue damage in real time. Fatigue tests were conducted at different stress ratios. Previously, static tensile tests were carried out to characterise the material and to calibrate the technique. The resistance measurements, conducted using the extensometer and the electrical contacts (four-probes method), were carried out in the same way for both tests.

The analysis of the static tests showed that the resistance measured by the electrical contacts decreases in the initial phases of the test, when the sample is in an elastic regime, subsequently increases linearly with the deformation, while it undergoes a reduction during the necking, in which the elongation of the sample and the change in resistivity in the plastic field prevail over the reduction in section.

The fatigue data, processed using the electrical contacts, showed an almost constant trend in resistance, unlike what was obtained previously on notched samples made of the same material. This result is justified by a significant effect of progressive plastic deformation which affects the cross section. The accumulation of plastic deformations was also highlighted through Vickers microhardness measurements. The results showed a progressive increase in hardness as the distance from the edge of the sample increased along the direction of the longitudinal fracture surface, highlighting an evident plastic deformation in the areas far from the edge of the specimen; while, along the direction perpendicular to the fracture surface, a progressive reduction was observed as the distance from the fracture surface increased.

Finally, the electrical resistance variations were also compared with the stiffness degradation and area under hysteresis loop evolutions. The electrical data results were consistent with mechanical data.

In general, the stress ratio, and therefore the average load applied, seem to not significantly influence the general trend obtained, as expected, but of course, to make more robust considerations further tests are required. The experimental results obtained instead using the extensometer knives as electrical terminals were affected by higher experimental errors, probably caused by the variation in the electrical contact resistance of the knives on the sample surface.

REFERENCE LIST

- (1) Palit Sagar, S., Das, S., Parida, N., Bhattacharya, D.K., *Scripta Materialia*, Vol. 55 (2), 2006, pp. 199–202.
- (2) Xia, Z., Okabe, T., Park, J.B., Curtin, W.A., Takeda, N., *Composite Science and Technology*, Vol. 63 (10), 2003, pp. 1411–22.
- (3) Mei, Z., Guerrero, V. H., Kowalik, D. P., Chung, D. D. L., *Polymer Composites*, Vol. 23, 2002, pp. 425–432.
- (4) Prasse, T., Michel, F., Mook, G., Schulte, K., Bauhofer, W., *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 61, 2001, 831–835.
- (5) Wang, S., Chung, D. D. L., *Composite Interfaces*, Vol. 9, 2002, pp. 51–60.

- (6) Klesnil, M., Lukáš P., *International Journal of Materials Research*, Vol. 84, 1982, pp. 291 – 291.
- (7) Sevostianov, I., Zagrai, A., Kruse, W., Hardee, H., *International Journal of Fracture*, Vol. 164, 2010, pp. 159–166.
- (8) Middleton, C. A., McCrory, J. P., Greene, R. J., Holford, K., Patterson, E. A., *Metals*, Vol. 9 (7), 2019, p. 748.
- (9) Rajic, N., Galea, S., *Structural Health Monitoring*, Vol. 14 (1), 2014, pp. 57–72.
- (10) Vassilopoulos, A. P., Keller, T., *Experimental Characterization of Fiber-Reinforced Composite Materials, Fatigue of Fiber-reinforced Composites*, Edited by A. P. Vassilopoulos, T. Keller, 2011.
- (11) Palumbo, D., De Finis, R., Saponaro, A., Nobile, R., Panella, F., Galietti, U., *Journal of Nondestructive Evaluation*, Vol. 40, 2021, p. 94.
- (12) De Finis, R., Palumbo, D., Galietti, U., *Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials & Structures*, Vol. 42 (2-3), 2018, pp. 267-283.
- (13) Omari, M. A., Sevostianov, I., *International Journal of Engineering Science*, Vol. 65, 2013, pp. 40–45.
- (14) Dattoma, V., Nobile, R., Panella, F. W., Saponaro, A., *Procedia Structural Integrity*, Vol. 24, 2019, pp. 583–592.
- (15) Park, J.-M., Lee, S.-I., DeVries, K. L., *Compos Part B Eng.*, Vol. 37, 2006, pp. 612-626.
- (16) Nobile, R., Saponaro, A., *International Journal of Fatigue*, Vol. 151, 2021, 106404.
- (17) Fischer, C., Arents, F. J., *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 46, 1993, pp. 319–323.
- (18) Schulte, K., Baron, Ch., *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 36, 1989, p. 63.
- (19) Motahhari, S., Cao, Y. M., Cameron, J., *Polymers and Polymer Composites*, Vol. 8, 2000, pp. 449–453.
- (20) Tanaka, K., Watanabe, T., *Applied Physics*, Vol. 11, 1972, pp. 1429-1439.
- (21) Lemaitre, J., Dufailly, J., *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol. 28, 1987, pp. 643-661.
- (22) Robins, B. A., Charsley, P., *Materials Science and Engineering*, Vol. 22, 1976, pp. 109-112.
- (23) Basinski, Z. S., Dugdale, J. S., Howie, A., *Philosophical Magazine*, Vol. 8 (96), 1963, pp. 1989-1997.
- (24) Starke, P., Klein, M., Eifler, D., *Procedia Engineering*, (2011) Vol. 10, 2011, pp. 698–703.
- (25) Lawson, L., Meshii, M., *Scripta Metallurgica*, Vol. 25, 1991, pp. 1713-1717.